

STRATEGIC INTERVENTION MATERIALS ON SUBJECT-VERB AGREEMENT: A TOOL FOR THE ENHANCEMENT OF STUDENTS' GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to develop Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) and investigate their effectiveness in teaching the least mastered skills on subject-verb agreement. The researcher utilized an experimental research design under the quantitative method. The study's respondents were 30 Tayawan National High School, Bayawan City students. The researcher utilized validated questionnaires and employed mean, t-test for dependent data, weighted mean, and Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Coefficient in treating the data. The study revealed that the pre-test performance of the students has "not met the expectations" while their post-test performance is at the "fairly satisfactory" level. It is also revealed that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test results of the students in the following areas: compound or singular subjects joined by 'and' are always plural, indefinite pronouns, collective nouns, and the expressions, "the number" and "a number." Moreover, the students perceive the effectiveness of the SIMs to a "very high" level, which is significantly related to their post-test performance. The use of SIMs was a successful intervention that helped students perform better on the posttest

Keywords: *SIMs, Subject-verb agreement, Least-learned skills, Grammatical competence*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical aspects of learning a language now is picking up grammar (Alahmadi, 2019). Understanding a language's structure is made possible by learning its grammar (Karam et al., 2020). On the other hand, learning English grammar as a second language has been scrutinized. Language learners' errors when producing a new language and the connection between these errors and the standards of English language learning and instruction have been the subject of numerous research (Alahmadi, 2019). Alahmadi also noted that the subject-verb rule is one of the grammatical constructions that fall under the syntax category in the language system and is seen as a challenge for L2 learners. Rido and Sari (cited in Khreisat 2022) emphasized that active physical activity and teacher-student connection are essential for learning, particularly language. However, during the COVID-19 pandemic, abrupt closures of all educational facilities have significantly hampered second language (ESL) learners learning English, specifically grammar abilities (Ying et al., 2021).

According to Education First (EF) (Baclig, 2020), the Philippines dropped from the 20th to the 27th spot in 2020's English Proficiency Index (EPI). With this, the Department of Education (DepEd) is now taking a proactive approach towards developing and harnessing students' potential by using instructional materials as what Republic Act No. 10533, otherwise known as "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013", section 10 of the curriculum development states that the production and development of locally produced teaching materials shall be encouraged as per DepEd Order No. 43, series of 2013.

There are some previous studies on grammatical enhancement using locally produced instructional materials, but the researcher observed that these studies used other techniques. For instance, Chun, Wui, Yunus, Rajasagaran, and Chun (2021) made use of improving Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) among Malaysian Year 3 ESL Learners using Gamified Flipped Home-Based Learning. Then, Miranda et al. (2021) developed an English Subject-Verb Agreement Mobile Learning Application for students who need help grasping subject-verb agreement rules. Unlike these studies, which require enough funds, a stable internet connection, gadgets, and other learning resources, the researcher creates teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) in subject-verb agreement after identifying the least-learned skills under the subject-verb agreement rules in order to help students improve their knowledge and proficiency in subject-verb agreement. Additionally, the researcher is interested in examining the impact of SVA SIMs that covers the following topics: compound (singular subjects joined by the conjunction "and"); indefinite pronouns; collective nouns; and the expressions "the number" and "a number" as a tool for improving student grammatical competence.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pre-test performance of the students in the following aspects of subject-verb agreement (SVA) before SIMs are used in teaching the concepts:
 - 1.1 compound or singular subjects joined by 'and';
 - 1.2 indefinite pronouns;
 - 1.3 collective nouns; and
 - 1.4 the expressions, "the number" and "a number"?
2. What is the post-test performance of the students in the aforementioned aspects of subject-verb agreement (SVA) after the use of SIMs?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the students as an indicator of their level of grammatical competence?
4. To what extent do students consider the effectiveness of SIMs in learning the concepts and/or aspects of subject-verb agreement?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' perceived effectiveness of SIMs and their post-test performance?

METHODOLOGY

The study utilized an experimental research design under the quantitative method. It is quantitative because the data were collected and interpreted before and after using the SIMs. In this study, the researcher determined the effectiveness of SIMs in the aforementioned aspects of the Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA). Hence, the experimental design was used as the effect of the independent variable, the utilization of SIMs, on the dependent variable; the students' level of grammatical competence was usually observed and recorded over some time to aid the researcher in drawing a reasonable conclusion regarding the relationship between the two variable types. The research process was categorized into three phases: (1.) Determination of Least-Mastered Aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA); (2.) Development and Validation of SIMs; and (3.) Final Phase. This study was conducted at Tayawan National High School of District 6, Bayawan City Division, in Brgy. Tayawan, Bayawan City, Negros Oriental, Philippines. The participants of this study were purposely selected because these were identified as Grade 7 students who failed below the standard criterion of 75% during the first quarterly test. The study used teacher-made Strategic Intervention Materials (SIMs) to re-teach the least-mastered aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) in English 7. Experts in the field of English teaching validated the SIMs. In validating the SIMs made by the researcher, the Standard Criteria for SIM (DepEd Memo No. 225, series of 2009, Enclosure No. 2) was used. After the validation process, the SIM underwent revisions to ensure its effectiveness. After the revisions, the researcher conducted a 48-item teacher-made test on the respondents for the pre-test. Then, they utilized the SIMs for the remediation, and lastly, they answered another 48-item questionnaire with similar questions used in the pre-test for their post-test. Each respondent's scores were used, and detailed statistical analysis was

conducted for data analysis. After gathering all the necessary data, the researcher tallied and tabulated them. These data were subjected to statistical treatment to arrive at reliable findings to answer each of the specific question in the problem. The tools that were utilized in analyzing and interpreting the data were the following: First, the percentage which was used to determine how a part is related to a whole. It was also utilized to identify whether the respondents have successfully passed or failed the intervention process. Next, the mean which was used in determining the scores of the students in each topic. Then, the weighted mean which was computed to determine the impact of SIMs used by learners in learning the least mastered skills. Alst-test for dependent data. This was used in identifying the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the students. This was selected since the data are in ratio scale. Also, Spearman's rank order correlation coefficient, utilized in identifying the relationship between the perceived extent of effectiveness of the SIMs and the post-test performance of the students. This study mainly focused on the determination of the effectiveness of SIMs in the following aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA): compound or singular subjects joined by 'and'; indefinite pronouns; collective nouns; and the expressions "the number" and "a number" after the introduction of SIMs. In addition, the data gathered were used to measure the effectiveness of using SIMs in teaching the least-mastered skills in SVA to enhance students' academic competence. The study's respondents were the Grade 7 students of Tayawan National High School in SDO-Bayawan City. Several limitations were set in this study. The first one was the learners' attendance during remediation sessions. Next was the learners' tendency to drop out of the remediation sessions. In addition, it was beyond the researcher's control regarding the learners' ability to finish or accomplish the module activities. Finally, other factors such as the physical and emotional aspects of the respondents and the tendency to decline their participation in the given activities which could affect the respondents' performance in this study were beyond the researcher's control.

RESULTS

Table 1
Pre-Test Performance of the Students (n = 30)

Aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement	Mean Rating	Verbal Description	Standard Deviation
• Compound or Singular Subjects Joined by 'and'	62.33	Did Not Meet Expectations	9.98
• Indefinite Pronouns	60.00	Did Not Meet Expectations	8.61
• Collective Nouns	62.67	Did Not Meet Expectations	8.48
• The Expressions, "the number" and "a number"	61.83	Did Not Meet Expectations	7.93
Overall	61.71	Did Not Meet Expectations	8.75

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	90% - 100%	Outstanding
	85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% - 84%	Satisfactory
	75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 2
Post-Test Performance of the Students (n = 30)

Aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement	Mean Rating	Verbal Description	Standard Deviation
• Compound or Singular Subjects Joined by 'and' are Always Plural	78.00	Fairly Satisfactory	7.02
• Indefinite Pronouns	76.33	Fairly Satisfactory	4.72
• Collective Nouns	74.17	Did Not Meet Expectations	3.96
• The Expressions, "the number" and "a number"	81.67	Satisfactory	10.20
Overall	77.54	Fairly Satisfactory	6.48

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description
	90% - 100%	Outstanding
	85% - 89%	Very Satisfactory
	80% - 84%	Satisfactory
	75% - 79%	Fairly Satisfactory
	74% and below	Did Not Meet Expectations

Table 3
Analysis Table on the Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Performance of the Students (n = 30)

Aspects of Subject-Verb Agreement	Pre-Test	Post-Test	D	t	p-value	Decision/Remark
• Compound or Singular Subjects Joined by 'and' are Always Plural	62.33	78.00	15.67	8.12	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)
• Indefinite Pronouns	60.00	76.33	16.33	11.06	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)
• Collective Nouns	62.67	74.17	11.50	7.87	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)
• The Expressions, "the number" and "a number"	61.83	81.67	19.84	10.15	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)
• Overall	61.71	77.54	15.83	16.70	0.000	Reject H_{01} (Significant)

Level of significance = 0.05

Table 4
Extent of Effectiveness of SIMs in Learning the Concepts and/or Aspects of Subject Verb Agreement (n = 30)

Indicators	w \bar{x}	VD	E $\bar{O}E$
1. The SIM helps me understand the rules of subject-verb agreement that were not understood during regular classroom teaching.	4.87	SA	VH
2. I want to use SIMs during remediation class.	4.87	SA	VH
3. I enjoyed reading and doing all the activities provided in the SIMs.	4.83	SA	VH
4. The SIM offers interesting activities.	4.77	SA	VH
5. The SIM is a student-friendly material.	4.70	SA	VH
6. The SIMs inspired and encouraged me to learn more concepts in subject-verb agreement.	4.70	SA	VH
7. After using the SIM, I learn the concepts that were not fully understood in the regular classroom instruction.	4.67	SA	VH
8. The instructions are simple and easy to follow.	4.60	SA	VH
9. Confusing concepts of subject-verb agreement were clearly presented.	4.53	SA	VH
10. I can set up my own pace in learning without feeling pressured about time.	4.23	SA	VH
Composite	4.68	SA	VH

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Effectiveness (E$\bar{O}E$)
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Very High (VH)
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree (A)	High (H)
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree (MA)	Moderate (M)
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree (D)	Low (L)
	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Very Low (VL)

Table 5

Relationship between the Students' Perceived Effectiveness of SIMs and Their Post-Test Performance (n= 30)

Variables	r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Extent of Effectiveness and Post-Test Performance	0.447	0.013	Reject H_{o2}	Significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend:	Value of r	Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
Between	± 0.50 to ± 1.00	± strong relationship
Between	± 0.30 to ± 0.49	± moderate relationship
Between	± 0.10 to ± 0.29	± weak relationship
Between	± 0.01 to ± 0.09	± very weak relationship

DISCUSSION

Table 1 reveals the pre-test performance of Grade 7 students in subject-verb agreement before using SIMs. As reflected, the overall data yield a failing performance (61.71) or students have not met the required expectations for the skills in subject-verb agreement, particularly rules in the compound or singular subjects joined by 'and,' indefinite pronouns, collective nouns, and expressions, "the number" and "a number." The results demonstrate that their pre-test transmuted ratings fall below the 75% passing rate required by DepEd Order No. 8 s. 2015 Policy Guidelines for K–12 Basic Education Classroom Assessment. This result is likewise evident in the study of Cordova et al. (2019), where the 200 Grade 7 students got lower scores in the pre-test. Likewise, the finding is in line with the result of Marribay (2022) where the pre-test result is 61.67% or below 75%. Likewise, study findings of Segarino (2022) disclosed that majority of both groups had very low scores in the pretest.

Table 2 shows the post-test performance of the students. It reveals that their mean rating in compound or singular subjects joined by "and" are always plural and indefinite pronouns are in the "fairly satisfactory" category with mean ratings of 78% and 76.33%, respectively. In addition, they have a "satisfactory" classification on the use of the expressions, "the number" and "a number" with mean rating of 81.67%. However, they have a rating of below 75% under collective nouns. Tran et al. (2021) state that comprehending and using collective nouns appears to be a challenging issue for English learners. The finding is in line with Karam et al. (2020), who conclude that students have problems and confusion in learning collective nouns as one of the grammatical categories in their study. Likewise, Pandapatan (2020) revealed that 75.7% of the students got incorrect answers when they were given a question using collective nouns as a subject. Synthesizing, students' overall performance falls in the "fairly satisfactory" description with

mean rating of 77.54%. The data signify that their performance passed the 75% standard criterion of DepEd. shows information on the age profile of students who took the Purposive Communication course. It indicates that out of the 265 participants, more than half of the respondents were between the ages of 20–21 with 53.58%. This is followed by ages 18–19 with 32.08% and ages 22 and above with 14.34%. The result suggests that the majority of the student respondents are within the age bracket between 20 and 21 years old. This is congruent with the findings of Cleofas and Rocha (2021) which stipulated that Filipino undergraduate students studying in college in the Philippines are between the age of 18–22 years old. Furthermore, according to CHED, the age range of students in the Philippines varies depending on the type of higher education institution (HEI) and program. For most undergraduate programs in universities and colleges, the minimum age requirement is 16 years old, while the maximum age is 30 years old. However, some HEIs may set different age limits based on their specific requirements and policies.

Table 3 presents the data in identifying the difference in the pre-test and post-test performance of the students. The data expose an increase in the post-test performance of the students after using the SIMs. To statistically test the difference, t-test for paired observation is applied. It is shown that all p-values in every aspect of the subject-verb agreement are less than the level of significance (0.05). This finding warrants the rejection of the null hypothesis. The finding means that a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the students exists. The result connotes that using SIMs is effective as it increases the scores of the students. However, in collective nouns, an increase in the student's scores is apparent, but they have a failing post-test rating. The result is similar to Marriby's (2022) findings, where the students' post-test scores had improved and attained mastery level, indicating that their performance responds favourably when SIM was used. These findings align with that of Benitez (2021), who stated that the respondents' performance levels significantly improved after using the intervention material. The result is further supported by the findings of Manalo (2019), Dumape(2019), and Benitez (2021). Cordova et al. (2019) also revealed that using competency-based SIMs improved learners' performance in the posttest.

Table 4 displays the extent of effectiveness of SIMs in learning the concepts/aspects of subject-verb agreement. It is disclosed in the composite weighted mean of 4.68 that the students can grasp how to use subject-verb agreement correctly. They are excited to participate during the remediation classes because of the exciting activities. The SIMs provides a detailed illustration in which the students follow the rules. The students also feel motivated and eager to learn more the subject-verb agreement concepts. SIMs help the students learn the aspects/rules of subject-verb agreement. It corresponds with Suarez and Casinillo's (2020) findings, which support the current results that SIMs are an excellent teaching strategy for boosting students' development in their least-learned skills. Bonitez (2021) also revealed that SIMs will improve and enhance the child's abilities, knowledge, and comprehension in a variety of subject areas, not just science and math, but also in other areas of the curriculum. The finding is parallel with the result of Alboruto (2017), SIMs are distributed in a similar manner to increase student participation and, as a result, encourage knowledge expansion. It was likewise affirmed by Arpilleda (2021)

that the SIM gave a positive impact in mastering the least-learned competency identified. The finding is in line with that of Cordova et al. (2019) who found that learners were enjoying and learning while using the SIM. It was discovered that students have previously acquired and improved their least mastered skills.

Table 5 shows the data analyzing the relationship between the students' perceived effectiveness of SIMs and their post-test performance. Using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation, the data indicate that the p-value (0.013) is less than the significance level (0.05). This finding allows the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result means a significant and moderate relationship exists between the paired variables. The finding also signifies that students who highly perceived the effectiveness of the SIMs tend to obtain better post-test performance. The data also demonstrated that the employment of SIMs was successful in increasing the respondents' level of performance. It corresponds with Bernido's (2020) findings, which showed a significant relationship between students' discernment of the effectiveness of SIMs and improved learners' performance. The findings are parallel with the result of Flores and Cacho (2020), which demonstrated that the respondents viewed SIM as effective as the respondents' English performance improved after using the intervention material. Finally, the finding is in line with Segarino et al. (2022), who revealed that students perceived that SIMs positively impacted student learning, leading to higher grades.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the use of Strategic Instructional Materials in improving the respondents' least-learned skills in Subject-Verb Agreement has somewhat helped them advance their understanding of the rules, specifically on Compound or singular subjects joined by 'and'; Indefinite pronouns; Collective nouns, and the expressions "the number" and "a number except on the rules on Collective nouns. Although the findings show that respondents have improved and their competence is classified as reasonably fairly satisfactory level and they find the SIM compelling; however, this could not be enough to conclude that this is an overwhelmingly positive result to say that the locally made SIMs have made a significant difference in the respondents' understanding about the rules of Subject-Verb Agreement. Moreover, some circumstances might hinder respondents from fully maximizing the SIMs' benefits due to the frequency of their attendance in the remediation classes using the SIMs in the Subject-Verb Agreement and the need for more technology integration in the SIM activities. Thus, consistency in attending the SIM sessions, integrating technology in the

activities in the SIM, and institutionalizing the SIM using cost-effective materials like indigenous materials would yield better respondents' performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the following are hereby recommended to school administrators, teachers, and parents:

School Administrators:

1. Recommend the SIMs to be utilized during the conduct of remediation classes to improve the least-learned skills of students in Subject-Verb Agreement.
2. Allocate funds for the production of SVA SIMs as a supplemental material.
3. Provide trainings/workshops on SIMs innovation in Subject-Verb Agreement.

Teachers:

4. Innovate/Enhance the activities in the SIMs by using technology or educational application(s) in learning other least-learned concepts and skills in grammar.
5. Initiate/integrate a 10-minute mental exercise in Subject-Verb Agreement called "SVA Rule of the Day" before the lesson proper daily until the students reached mastery of the rules.
6. Use indigenous materials such as plastic bottles, soap or milk boxes, coconut shells, and the like in presenting Subject-verb agreement rules/aspects to learners in a creative way.

Parents:

7. Seek the support of parents in the planning and implementation of remediation classes in subject-verb agreement to be conducted in a regular basis until the learners reached the mastery criterion.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

I, Vivian S. Belarmino, the author of this study, hereby declare that all necessary measures were taken to ensure ethical standards in the conduct of this research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and they were explicitly informed about the nature and purpose of the study. Participants were assured of their freedom to withdraw from the study at any stage without facing any consequences. Anonymity was diligently maintained, and all identifying information was kept confidential to protect the privacy of the respondents.

The well-being of the participants was a top priority throughout the research process. Steps were taken to minimize any potential discomfort or harm that may arise from their involvement in the study. Additionally, no conflicts of interest were present that could compromise the objectivity and integrity of the research. The study was conducted with utmost transparency, and any potential bias in the interpretation of the findings was rigorously avoided.

Furthermore, this research adheres to the principles of academic integrity, and plagiarism was strictly prohibited. Originality and honesty were maintained in the formulation and

presentation of ideas, ensuring the credibility of the study. The results obtained from this research will be used solely for academic and research purposes, and no information will be misused or manipulated for any other agenda.

In conclusion, this declaration affirms the commitment to ethical standards, transparency, and academic integrity in the execution and reporting of the research study.

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REFERENCES

- Alahmadi, N. (2019). A study of grammatical errors of subject verb agreement in writing made by Saudi learners. *International Journal of English Language and Linguistics Research*, 7(6), 48-59.
- Alboruto, V. M. (2017, May). Beating the numbers through strategic intervention materials (SIMs): Innovative science teaching for large classes. In AIP Conference Proceedings (Vol. 1848, No. 1, p.060014). AIP Publishing LLC.
- Arpilleda, A. (2021). Strategic Intervention Material: A Tool in Enhancing Grade Nine Students' Mathematical Performance. <http://consortiacademia.org/10-5861-ijrse-2021-5051/>
- Baclig, C.E. (2020). Philippine drops further in global English proficiency ranking. *Inquirer.Net*. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1362951/philippines-drops-further-in-global-english-proficiency-rankings>
- Bernido, R. (2023). Use of Strategic Intervention Materials (SIM) in Adding Integers: An Action Research. Available at SSRN 4426854.
- Bonitez, A. G. (2021). Effectiveness of Science Strategic Intervention Material in Elevating the Performance Level of Grade Seven Students. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Education and Society*, 3(2), 18-31. <https://myjms.mohe.gov.my/index.php/ijares/article/view/13481>
- Chun, T. W., Rajasagaran, S., Wui, J. W. J., & Yunus, M. M. (2021). The Effectiveness of Gamified Flipped Home-Based Learning in Improving Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) Among Malaysian Year 3 ESL Learners. *International Invention, Innovative & Creative (InIIC) Conference*. http://www.mnnfpublisher.com/uploads/4/6/9/3/46931833/proceedingsiniic_conf_series_2_2021.pdf#page=12
- Cordova, R. C., Medina, J. G. D., Ramos, T. R., & Alejo, A. R. (2019). Effectiveness of Competency-Based Strategic Intervention Materials in English 7. *Journal of Science Teachers and Educators*, 2(1). <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/research-congress-proceedings/2019/lii-II-019.pdf>
- Department of Education Memorandum No. 117, s. 2005. "Training Workshop on Strategic Interventions for Successful Learning". https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2005/04/DM_s2005_117.pdf
- Department of Education Memorandum No. 39, series of 2012. Policy Guidelines on Addressing Learning Gaps and Implementing a Reading and Writing Program in Secondary Schools Effective School Year SY) 2012-2013. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/05/11/do-39-s-2012-policy-guidelines-on-addressing-learning-gaps-and-implementing-a-reading-and-writing-program-in-secondary-schools-effective-school-year-sy-2012-2013/>
- Department of Education Order No. 43, series of 2013. Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of Republic Act No. 10533 Otherwise Known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2013/09/24/do-43-s-2013-implementing-rules-and->

- regulations-irr-of-republic-act-no-10533-otherwise-known-as-the-enhanced-basic- education-act-of-2013/
- Dumape, J. L. (2020). Utilization of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) in Teaching Grammar Among Grade 10 Students. *Lamdag*, 11(1),1-1. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=16515>
- EF Education. (2021). Indefinite pronoun. <https://www.ef.edu/english-resources/english-grammar/indefinite-pronouns>
- Karam, A., Hamid, A., Ali, S. S., Rahat, L. (2020). Problems in The Acquisition of English Nouns by Undergraduate Level Learners. *Ilkogretim Online*, 19(3), 3678-3693.
- Khreizat, M.N. (2022). English Language Learning Strategies during COVID-19 in the Middle East: A Systematic Review. *Arab World English Journal*, 13 (1) 56-71. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol13no1.4>
- Manalo, G. (2019). Development of Strategic Intervention Material to Uphold Grade Six Learners' Academic Progress in English at Mainit Elementary School." *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2B). <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/5634>
- Marribay, J. (2022). Project SOLE: Sharpening of the least mastered skills in Learning English through SIM-Based Learning Activities. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 3(1), 26-33. <https://ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/89>
- Miranda, J., Dianelo, R., Yabut, A., Paguio, C., Cruz, A. D., Mangahas, H., & Malabasco, K. (2021). Development of INSVAGRAM: An English Subject-Verb Agreement Mobile Learning Application. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, 16(19), 219-234. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i19.24071>
- Pandapatan, A. M. (2020). Analysis of the subject-verb agreement ability among Indonesian English major students as EFL learners. *Journal of English Language Studies*, 5(2), 127- 143.
- Republic Act No. 10533 (RA 10533). Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. <https://ovap.peac.org.ph/about/ra10533>.
- Segarino, G. M., Labisig, J., Calmerin, L., & Cabello, C. (2022). SIMS as Intervention in Enriching the Teaching of Fundamental Operations in Mathematics: An Action Research. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 5(1), 11-20.
- Suarez, M. & Casinillo, L. (2020). Effect of Strategic Intervention Material (SIM) on Academic Performance: Evidence from Students of Science VI. *Review of Socio-Economic Research and Development Studies*, 4(1), 20-32, 2020. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3804203
- Tran, T. T. O., & Bui, T. V. T. (2021). The Semantic Features of Collective Nouns in English. *International Journal of TESOL & Education*, 1(3), 130-141. <https://ijte.org/index.php/journal/article/view/84>
- World Health Organization (WHO, 2020). Coronavirus disease (COVID-19). https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_1

World Health Organization (WHO, 2020). Archived: WHO Timeline - COVID-19.
https://www.who.int/health-topics/coronavirus#tab=tab_1

Ying, Y. , Siang, W. and Mohamad, M. (2021) The Challenges of Learning English Skills and the Integration of Social Media and Video Conferencing Tools to Help ESL Learners Coping with the Challenges during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Literature Review. *Creative Education*, 12, 1503-1516. doi: 10.4236/ce.2021.127115.